

Drivers of Non-Performing Loans in Ethiopian Commercial Banks: An Empirical Investigation

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Abstract

This paper examines the bank-specific and macro-economic determinants of non-performing loans (NPLs) in Ethiopian commercial banks from 2008 to 2022. The study uses an explanatory research design to identify cause-and-effect relationships between NPLs and their determinants. Feasible generalized least squares panel regression was applied to data from nine commercial banks (one public and eight private). The analysis revealed that return on assets had a negative and significant impact on NPLs. Conversely, the loan-to-deposit ratio had a positive and significant impact, while the efficiency ratio had a negative but statistically insignificant effect. Among macroeconomic factors, GDP, the effective tax rate, and lending interest rates had a positive and significant impact on NPLs, while government expenditure and broad money supply had negative and significant effects. Inflation rate had a positive but insignificant effect. The study suggests that bank loan officers should monitor borrowers' circumstances to prevent loan defaults, while the National Bank of Ethiopia should adopt expansionary monetary policy, and the government should implement expansionary fiscal policies to reduce NPLs levels.

Key words: Bank Specific Factors, Macro-economic Factors, Non-performing Loan

1. Introduction

The primary functions provided by banks include accepting deposits, facilitating domestic and international money transactions, and making a profit from these operations. Lending, managing deposits, transferring funds, and acting as agents or middlemen are some of the most important roles that banks play. Among these, lending serves as the foundation for the banking sector. Loans typically constitute 50-75 percent of a bank's assets, making them the largest source of operating income but also the greatest source of risk (Koch & MacDonald, 2014). However, banks are seriously threatened by a reduction in asset quality, particularly if there is no mechanism in place for quickly identifying the problem. It is one of the main reasons why banks collapse. Non-performing loans are the outcome of poor asset quality, which can seriously impair a bank's financial position and have a detrimental effect on its general operations (Epure & Lafuente, 2014).

Profitability is the primary objective of any firm. Because of this, every asset created while a business is in operation should generate revenue for the company. Since loans are the primary activity of commercial banks and typically their primary asset and revenue stream, banks must conduct a comprehensive analysis of loan management in relation to the banking industry (Daniel & Wandera, 2013). Furthermore, a rise in non-performing loans is associated with flaws in the financial system, which increases the bank's exposure to credit risk. This has prompted numerous studies to investigate the factors that determine non-performing loans of banks, including macroeconomic and bank-specific factors in developed and developing economies (Ahmad & Bashir, 2013; Arham et al., 2020; Calice, 2012; Ghosh, 2017; Khemraj & Pasha, 2009; Louzis et al., 2012; Olarewaju, 2020; Saba et al., 2012). Non-performing loans have a detrimental impact on banks' balance sheets, diminishing their profitability and adding to the general decline in the financial industry (Ghosh, 2017). In order to mitigate the risks associated with bad loans, African countries concurred that higher exposure to loan loss responsibility was necessary. Nonetheless, NPLs have been steadily rising in some African countries (Olaewaju, 2020).

Saba et al. (2012) studied the determinants of NPLs in the U.S. Banking sector. The study concludes that the rate of non-performing loans (NPLs) in the U.S. banking industry is mainly determined by macroeconomic factors, especially interest rates and real GDP per capita. Higher interest rates may induce more cautious lending, which lowers default risks, according to the inverse relationship between interest rates and non-performing loans (NPLs). Real GDP per capita shows how economic growth

improves borrowers' ability to repay loans and has a strong correlation with non-performing loans (NPLs). Besides, Khemraj & Pasha (2009) applied a fixed effect model to a panel dataset in an effort to determine the causes of non-performing loans (NPLs) in Guyana's banking sector. The results of their empirical study corroborate the notion that the amount of non-performing loans is significantly affected by macro-factors, such as an increase in real GDP and the real effective exchange rate. Every country's economy is at risk from non-performing loans, as demonstrated by the financial crises these loans sparked in East Asian countries, the US, and Sub-Saharan Africa (Adebola et al., 2011).

Despite ongoing efforts to reduce non-performing loans, many Ethiopian lending institutions continue to face a rising number of NPLs. For instance, as of June 30, 2021, several banks reported significant NPL ratios, including Zemen Bank at 9.1%, Cooperative Bank of Oromia at 6.4%, Bank of Abyssinia at 6.3%, and Awash International Bank at 6.9%. Additionally, the Commercial Bank of Ethiopia recorded an NPL ratio of 8.2%, while Lion International Bank, Nib International Bank, United Bank, Wegagen Bank, and Dashen Bank reported 6.8%, 7.2%, 5.7%, 7.5%, and 5.4%, respectively (Bank's annual report 2021/2022). The issue of non-performing loans has affected lending institutions as well as the economy; Ethiopia is no exception. All Ethiopian banks must maintain a non-performing loan ratio below five percent as per the country's financial regulation framework (NBE, 2024).

Essentially, the issue of non-performing loans is left unresolved. In that case, it can compound into a financial crisis, where the loans exceed bank capital in a relatively large number of banks. Moreover, to maintain non-performing loans, it is necessary to understand its causes. Based on this, this study attempts to extend the existing body of literature in developing economies by exploring the effect of bank-specific factors and government policies on non-performing loans of commercial banks in Ethiopia. This study makes a significant contribution to existing knowledge in several ways. First, the study examines the monetary and fiscal policy-related factors influencing non-performing loans at selected commercial banks in Ethiopia. Second, the study also analyzes the effect of bank-specific factors on non-performing loans in Ethiopia. Third, the study is based on a new dataset and methodological specifications. The findings of the study will not only be helpful for the regulators of each economy examined but also will help the top management of banks to set up proper loan structures, review internal banking operations, and alert the borrowers to what individual policies to adopt.

The rest of the study is organized as follows: Section 2 deals with the theoretical framework and provides an empirical review. Following that, Section 3 explains the research methodology. Section 4 presents descriptive statistics and empirical analysis. Section 5 makes the final conclusions and suggestions.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Theoretical framework

In the past decades, there have been significant advances in theoretical understanding on the role of credit markets. These advances have evolved from a paradigm that emphasizes imperfect information and enforcement problems (Hoff & Stiglitz, 1990). They pointed out that borrowers and lenders may have differential access to information concerning a project's risk and may form different risk appraisals. So, what is clearly evident in the credit market is the presence of asymmetric information, where the borrower has detailed knowledge of the expected return and risk of their specific project, while the lender is only aware of the expected return and risk associated with the average project in the economy.

Lending institutions, such as banks, commonly face four major challenges in their credit activities. First, they must determine the risk level of potential borrowers, a problem known as adverse selection. Second, they need to ensure that borrowers will use the loan appropriately, enabling them to repay it, which addresses the moral hazard issue. Third, in cases where borrowers declare their inability to repay, lenders must assess how the project actually performed. Finally, banks must devise methods to enforce repayment if borrowers are reluctant to fulfill their obligations. These challenges arise due to imperfect information and weak enforcement mechanisms, leading to inefficiencies in the credit market and increased loan defaults (Ghatak & Guinnane, 1999). This study is grounded in information asymmetry theory, which highlights the essential information that both lenders and business owners should be

aware of regarding potential risks and returns associated with investments for which resources are allocated. Information asymmetry refers to the extent to which bank managers have more knowledge about a firm than investors as a whole.

2.2. Empirical studies

The study conducted by Nkusu (2011), Adebola et al. (2011), and Berge & Boye (2007) found a positive correlation between lending rate and NPLs. An increase in interest rate weakens the loan payment capacity of the borrower; therefore, non-performing loans and bad loans are positively correlated with the interest rates (Nkusu, 2011). Farhan et al. (2012) argued that banks with aggressive lending policies charging high interest rates from the borrowers incur greater non-performing loans. The findings reveal that interest rate, energy crisis, unemployment, inflation, and exchange rate have a significant positive relationship with NPLs, meaning that an increase in these factors leads to a rise in loan defaults. Conversely, GDP growth has a significant negative relationship with NPLs, indicating that stronger economic growth improves borrowers' ability to repay loans, thus reducing NPLs.

Ebenezer & Omar (2016) investigates the effect of credit risk on the profitability of commercial banks in Nigeria. Using data from eight Systemically Important Banks (SIBs) for the period 2011 to 2014, the study employs a panel data analysis to explore the relationship between credit risk indicators (non-performing loans, total debt to assets, and debt to equity ratios) and profitability, measured by return on equity (ROE). The results reveal that non-performing loans negatively and significantly impact profitability, indicating poor credit management policies. However, the debt-to-asset ratio shows a negative but insignificant relationship with profitability, while the debt-to-equity ratio has a positive but insignificant effect. The study concludes that effective credit risk management is crucial for improving the profitability of Nigerian banks, recommending a refocus on managing financial risks to ensure sustainable growth.

The study by Ghosh (2017) examines the impact of non-performing loans (NPLs) on U.S. product and labour markets using time-series data from 1984 to 2016. The methodology involves both single-equation Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regressions and Vector Autoregressions (VARs), allowing the study to assess both immediate and persistent effects of NPLs on economic activity. The findings show that an increase in total NPLs reduces U.S. GDP growth, with the construction sector being the most affected. Similarly, NPLs significantly decrease employment growth in financial activities and construction sectors. The conclusions emphasize that high NPLs constrain banks' ability to lend, which in turn hampers economic growth, particularly in sensitive sectors like construction. The study calls for regulatory authorities to monitor NPLs vigilantly to mitigate potential real-sector losses.

Tarchouna et al. (2022) examine the impact of corporate governance on non-performing loans (NPLs) across different bank sizes in U.S. commercial banks from 2000 to 2013. Using dynamic panel GMM estimation, the study analyzes 184 banks divided into small, medium, and large categories based on asset size. The research finds that small banks, which rely heavily on personal connections, tend to have weaker corporate governance, leading to higher NPLs. Medium-sized banks exhibit stronger governance, improving loan quality. In contrast, despite having strong liquidity, large banks engage in excessive lending due to neutralized governance, resulting in higher NPLs.

The study by Arham et al. (2020) examines the influence of macroeconomic cyclical indicators and country governance on non-performing loans (NPLs) in Emerging Asian countries. Using a panel regression methodology, the researchers analyzed data from ten countries between 2007 and 2017. The baseline findings indicate that unemployment and real interest rates positively and significantly impact NPLs, while inflation and total external debt-to-GDP have adverse effects. The study introduces an interaction analysis with country governance variables (corruption control, government effectiveness, and regulatory quality), demonstrating that solid governance mitigates the adverse effects of macroeconomic cycles on NPLs. The results emphasize that governance is crucial in reducing credit risk in these economies. Overall, the research contributes valuable insights for policymakers and banking sector managers to improve NPL management in Emerging Asia.

The study by Ferreira (2022) investigates the determinants of non-performing loans (NPLs) across 80 countries from 1999 to 2019 using panel data analysis. The findings reveal that high profitability, stable market conditions, and economic growth are associated with lower NPL ratios, indicating healthier banking sectors. Conversely, higher NPL ratios are linked to increased bank costs, market concentration, and stricter bank regulations. The study also finds that bank regulation has effectively reduced NPLs, particularly in non-high-income and non-OECD countries, after the 2008 financial crisis. The research concludes that promoting economic growth is crucial for minimizing NPLs and mitigating financial risks.

The study by Louzis et al. (2012) utilizes dynamic panel data methods to investigate the macroeconomic and bank-specific determinants of non-performing loans (NPLs) in the Greek banking sector, focusing on different loan categories: mortgage, business, and consumer loans. The methodology integrates macroeconomic variables such as GDP growth, unemployment, and interest rates alongside bank-specific factors like management efficiency and capital adequacy. The findings indicate that macroeconomic conditions, especially GDP growth and unemployment rates, significantly influence NPLs across all loan types, with business loans being the most responsive. Mortgage loans, however, show the least sensitivity to macroeconomic fluctuations.

Lee et al. (2022) examine the determinants of non-performing loans (NPLs) in Taiwanese banks, focusing on the interplay between corporate governance and macroeconomic factors. The researchers employed a panel smooth transition regression (PSTR) model to analyze data from 32 Taiwanese-listed firms between 2008 and 2015. The study finds that corporate governance variables, such as share collateralization by directors (SCD) and related party transactions (RPT), have a significant positive relationship with NPLs, particularly under low GDP conditions. The analysis also reveals a negative relationship between macroeconomic growth indicators (GDP and manufacturing production index) and NPLs. The study concludes that banks should not only focus on firms' financial performance but also give substantial attention to corporate governance practices, especially during periods of economic downturn, to mitigate credit risks effectively.

Furthermore, this study intended to consider monetary and fiscal-related factors to assess fiscal and monetary policy's impact on non-performing loans (combined effect on non-performing loans). Likewise, due to the rapid expansion of banking institutions in Ethiopia, it is better to conduct this investigation to ensure their continuous operation because non-performing loans lead to huge losses on bank profit in particular and the country's economy in general. This study, therefore, seeks to fill this gap by establishing the link between nonperforming loans and its determinants (bank-specific and macroeconomic factors) in the case of commercial banks in Ethiopia.

3. 3. Method, Data, and Analysis

The study employed an explanatory research design because the study is concerned in determining the cause-and-effect relationship between variables by using the quantitative method, as it is the best approach to obtain information about causal relationships, allowing to assess the correlation (relationship) between one variable and another with structured record reviews financial information collected from secondary data such as National Bank of Ethiopia publication, annual reports of the banks, Ministry of Finance and Economic Development and other relevant sources. This method is appropriate to meet the research objective that uses panel data.

3.1. Sampling and Data Collection

For this study, the target population constitutes all commercial banks registered by the National Bank of Ethiopia (NBE) and under operation in the country. Currently, the country has one state-owned bank and twenty-six private commercial banks operating throughout the country. As Kothari (2004) emphasized, a well-designed sample should be feasible, considering the time and financial resources available for the research. Accordingly, from the total number of commercial banks in Ethiopia within the study area, those that have been in operation for at least fifteen years and have audited financial statements were selected for this study using a non-probability (judgmental) sampling technique. The banks considered in this study were the Commercial Bank of Ethiopia, Awash Bank, Dashen Bank, Bank of Abyssinia, Wegagen Bank, United Bank, Nib International Bank, Cooperative Bank of Oromia, and Lion International Bank.

The study used secondary sources of data. The data sources for the study were taken from the National Bank of Ethiopia (NBE), the Ministry of Finance and Economic Development (MOFED), and the annual audited financial statements such as the balance sheet and income statement of selected commercial banks. This study used descriptive statistics and inferential statistics based on panel data. A descriptive analysis describes patterns of behavior or relevant aspects of phenomena and detailed information about each variable. Therefore, each variable's mean, minimum, maximum, and standard deviations were used. Then, the collected data was processed and analyzed through STATA version 17 software packages. Thus, regression results would be presented with the appropriate test statistics in a tabular form.

3.2. Model Specification

The nature of the data used in this study enables the researcher to use the panel regression model. The general formula used for this model is:

$$NPLsit = \beta_0 + \beta_{ixit} + \mu_{it} \dots \dots \dots 3.1$$

In this model, $NPLsit$ represents the non-performing loans of bank i at time t . The term β_0 denotes the intercept for the independent variables Xit , which are the various factors influencing non-performing loans. Additionally, μ_{it} captures other unobserved variables that may affect non-performing loans. The time dimension, t , spans from 1 to 15 years, enabling the model to analyze trends and variations in non-performing loans over this extended period. Based on the above general formula, the following model is used to test the hypothesis, which shows the dependence of non-performing loans on different independent variables this are:

$$NPLsit = \beta_0 + \beta_1LTDit + \beta_2OEOIRit + \beta_3ROAit + \beta_4 M2GDPit + \beta_5ETRit + \beta_6GDPit + \beta_7IRit + \beta_8 LIRit + \beta_9GEit \dots \dots \dots 3.2$$

The model investigates the determinants of non-performing loans ($NPLsit$) for bank i during time period t . It includes key variables such as the loan-to-deposit ratio ($LTDit$) and operational inefficiency ratio ($OEOIRit$) for the same period, which indicate the bank's financial management and efficiency levels. The return on assets ($ROAit$) for bank i during time period t is included to represent profitability. Macroeconomic factors, such as the broad money to GDP ratio ($M2GDPit$), effective tax rate ($ETRit$), gross domestic product ($GDPit$), inflation rate ($IRit$), lending interest rate ($LIRit$), and government expenditure ($GEit$) during the same period, are also integrated into the model to capture broader economic influences. The intercept (β_0) represents baseline effects, while μ_{it} captures unobserved factors impacting non-performing loans.

The empirical models outlined above were estimated using the following econometric techniques. To identify the best model for this study, it is essential to compare the outcomes produced by each technique. These techniques include the Fixed Effect Model, Random Effect Model, and the Feasible generalized least square estimation technique (FGLS). The FGLS is applied to overcome problems of autocorrelation and heteroskedasticity, if found present in either the random or fixed effect. The study employed the Hausman test to decide between the fixed and random effect models.

The problems of heteroscedasticity (usually associated with cross-sectional data) and autocorrelation (usually time series data) are sometimes observed even in panel datasets. The Breusch and Pagan Lagrangian multiplier test for heteroscedasticity in random effects regression and the Wooldridge test or the Lagrange-Multiplier test for autocorrelation model are employed to test for heteroscedasticity and autocorrelation, respectively. A test for the severity of multicollinearity is carried out using the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) technique. Since estimates generated by the random or fixed effects models become inefficient and inconsistent when heteroskedasticity, is present, this study employs the Feasible generalized least square estimation technique (FGLS).

3.3. Description of variables

To achieve the study's objective, panel data from 2008 to 2022 were gathered from the annual reports of the National Bank of Ethiopia (NBE) and the Ministry of Finance and Economic Development (MOFED). The study adopts non-performing loans as the dependent variable. Independent variables for this study are bank-specific characteristics and government policy-related factors that could influence the trends of non-performing loans.

3.3.1. Non-performing Loans

This study used only one dependent variable, which is non-performing loans. According to the International Monetary Fund (IMF, 2009), a non-performing loan (NPL) is any loan in which payments of interest and principal are past due by 90 days or more, or at least 90 days of interest payment have been capitalized, refinanced or delayed by agreement, or payments are less than 90 days overdue. NPL is a loan that delays for the payment of principal and interest for more than 90 days. It is measured or indicated by the amount of NPLs to gross loans.

3.3.2. Bank specific variables

Return on Asset (ROA): The return on assets ratio, often called the return on total assets, is a profitability ratio that measures the net income produced by total assets during a period by comparing net income to the average total assets. Therefore, the return on assets ratio measures how effectively the bank can earn a return on its investment in assets. In this regard, many scholars found a negative association between a bank's financial performance and the bank's NPLs (Louzis et al., 2012; Nikolaidou & Vogiazas, 2014). Thus, this ratio is expected to have a negative relationship with NPLs in this study. **Loan to deposit (LTD):** a ratio used to determine the number of loans that a bank has utilized to the number of current deposits on hand at that same time. Referring to the research findings of Louzis et al. (2012) that show loan to deposit ratio positively affects NPL and supporting the claim that an increase in deposits as compared to the loans shows that banks are more concerned with the quality of loans rather than the quantity and lend only to the quality borrowers. Thus, it represents a bank's preference for credit. In this study, this ratio is expected to have a positive relation with NPLs. **Inefficiency (OEOIR):** Inefficiency is measured as the ratio between operating expenses and operating incomes. It is also termed as operating expenses to operating income ratio. High value of this ratio indicates poor management efficiency. Inefficiency measured by operating expense to operating income (Garr, 2013). Therefore, as shown by Garr (2013), this study expects a positive coefficient of the inefficiency.

3.3.3 Macroeconomic Variables

The rate of inflation is the rate at which a currency's buying power declines as prices rise across the economy. It represents a widespread and sustained increase in the expense of living. Empirically, Fofack (2005) revealed that non-performing loans and inflation were positively correlated in many Sub-Saharan African countries. Rising inflation makes borrowing money more expensive, which damages loan portfolio quality. This study anticipates that inflation rates will have a direct, positive impact on NPLs. Gross domestic product is the most comprehensive indicator of a country's economic performance, encompassing everything produced by its people and businesses. Real GDP growth serves as a key measure of an economy's health and stability, typically expressed as an annual percentage. Referring to the research findings of Saba et al. (2012) and Khemraj & Pasha (2009), GDP growth has an inverse association with the level of non-performing loans (NPLs) of commercial banks. As GDP grows, NPLs tend to decline, reflecting stronger economic conditions. Consequently, this study expects nonperforming loan levels to be negatively correlated with GDP growth. **Lending interest rate:** represents the weighted average of interest charged on loans and advances, essentially reflecting the cost of borrowing. In simple terms, the interest rate is the price borrowers pay for using funds from lenders. In this general setting, a higher interest rate causes even more adverse selection, meaning that it raises the possibility that the lender will lend to borrowers with poor credit histories, which in turn raises NPLs (Ahmad & Bashir, 2013; Khemraj & Pasha, 2009; Louzis et al., 2012). This study expects lending rates to have a positive effect on NPLs.

Effective tax rate: the rate which would be paid by a taxpayer on his tax if it was charged at a constant rate rather than progressive. i.e., the effective tax rate is the average rate at which the bank is taxed on

the earned income. According to Khan et al. (2018), A positive relationship was analyzed between the Tax rate and the NPL ratio. The higher the tax rate is, the lesser the ability of the borrower to repay the loans. This study expects positive relationships between tax rates and NPLs. Broad money supply (M2): Money supply is a part of monetary policy that aims to encourage economic growth by targeting the amount of money circulating in the market. The greater the amount of money in circulation (M2), the higher the public purchasing power, which can increase the level of public consumption and, in the long run, encourage high CPI levels, ultimately affecting the business world. Empirically, Nikolaidou & Vogiazas (2014) found an antagonistic relationship between money supply and NPLs. This study expects an inverse relationship between broad money supply and NPLs. The variable can be measured by the ratio of broad money supply to GDP. Government expenditure (G.E.) is part of the fiscal policy that aims to promote economic growth and depends on the amount of government revenue. If the government has set a policy to buy goods and services, the government's costs to implement the policy reflect the government's expenditure. If the government has more expenditure, the people of a region would have a greater income. Touny & Shehab (2015) viewed the inverse relationship between government spending and NPLs. This study expects a negative coefficient of the government expenditure. The ratio of total government expenditure to GDP can measure the variable.

Table 1. Summary of Potential factors that influence the level of NPLs, corresponding measures, and hypothetic effects on non-performing loans.

Factors	Symbol	Measurement	Expected sign
Non-performing loans	NPLs	NPLs to gross loan	
Return on asset	ROA	Net profit to total asset	Negative
Inefficiency	OEOIR	Expense to income ratio	Positive
Liquidity ratio	LTD	Total loan to deposit	Positive
Lending interest rate	LIR	Lending rate of bank	Positive
Inflation	IR	CPI	Positive
Gross domestic product	GDP	Real GDP growth rate (in %)	Negative
Effective tax rate	ETR	Tax to net income before tax	Positive
Broad money	M2	Broad money (M2) over GDP	Negative
Government expenditure	GE	Government expenditure as% of GDP	Positive

Source: Table by authors

4. Results and Discussion

4.1. Descriptive Statistics

The summary of descriptive statistics intended to give general descriptions of the data (both dependent and independent variables) is presented in Table 2. The total number of observations for each variable is 135 (i.e., data for nine banks from 2008 to 2022). Accordingly, each variable's mean, median, standard deviation, minimum, and maximum values were used to show the overall trend of the data over the period under consideration.

Table 2. Summary of descriptive statistics for dependent and independent variable

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
NPLs	135	.0524171	.1070029	0	0.1475
ROA	135	.0272538	.0120425	-.0188	.0623
LTD	135	.6038855	.1228915	.3	.67
OEOIR	135	.3004	.0509631	.03	.5
IR	135	.1760513	.0957804	.074	.364
LIR	135	.1224786	.0068426	.1	.15
GDP	135	.0992393	.0121461	.077	.118
GovExp	135	.179	.0314665	.1	.36
M2	135	.3025983	.0568137	.14	.44
Tax rate	135	.5962085	.172345	.17	.33

Source: Table by authors

As can be seen from table 2, for the total sample, the mean of NPLs was 5.24% with a minimum of 0% and a maximum of 14.75%. This indicates that, from the total loans that Ethiopia commercial banks disbursed, an average of 5.24% were being default or uncollected over the sample period. According to Ethiopian context, the banking sectors are required to maintain the ratio of NPLs at least below 5%

(NBE, 2008). However, as indicated above in table 2, the NPLs of commercial banks in Ethiopia are more than the required threshold. Thus, NPLs problem are still serious for commercial banks in Ethiopia. The disparity between the minimum 0% and the maximum 75% of NPLs indicate the margin that NPLs ratio of Ethiopia commercial banks ranged over the sample period. The standard deviation (10.7%) of NPLs also shows the existence of high variation among Ethiopia commercial banks in terms their loan recovering capacity.

As far as profitability ratio concerned, ROA records a minimum of -1.88 and maximum of 6.2% with a mean value of 2.72% implies that on average firms can able to get 2.72% of return on each birr invested in asset. In case high ROA indicates better performance in the management of available asset. Regarding LTD ratio that measured by total loans divided by total deposits, it ranges from a minimum of 30% to a maximum of 67%. It has a mean of 60.38% and standard deviation of (12.28%). OEOIR also measured by operating expense divided by operating income presents a minimum of 30% and maximum of 50% with a mean value and standard deviation of 30% and 5.09% respectively. The mean value of real GDP growth rate is 9.92 % indicating the average real growth rate of the country's economy over the past thirteen years was a good one with averagely on 9.92 percent, there was a stable economic growth because the standard deviation is 1.2 percent. The maximum growth of the economy was recorded as 11.8% and a minimum of 7.7% respectively. Furthermore, LIR demonstrates a minimum of 10 and maximum of 15% with a mean value 12.24% showing 0.68% standard deviations. And inflation rate ranges from minimum values of 7.4% to a maximum of 36.4% and with mean value of 17.6%. Finally, Government expenditure ranges from minimum values of 10% to a maximum of 36%, with mean value of 17.9%. Broad money supply ranges from minimum values of 14% to a maximum of 44%, and effective tax rate ranges from a minimum of 17% to maximum of 33% with a mean value of 59.6%. To sum up, tax rate had the highest standard deviation (17.24%) whereas lending interest rate had the lowest standard deviation of (0.68%) shows that the mean value of lending interest rate was deviated from its mean to up and down by 0.68%.

4.2. Correlation Analysis

The correlation coefficient is a measure of the strength and direction of a linear relationship between two variables. The correlation coefficient can take on values between minus one and plus one. A coefficient of 1 indicates a perfectly positive association, where an increase in one variable causes an equal and opposite increase in the other. Alternatively, if the value is -1, it indicates a perfectly negative relationship where the value of one variable increases while the value of the other lowers. The absence of a linear relationship between the variables is indicated by a coefficient of zero (Brooks, 2008).

Table 3. Pearson's correlation of variables

	NPL	ROA	LTD	OEOIR	IR	LIR	GDP	GovExp	M2	Taxrate
NPL	1.0000									
ROA	-0.3304	1.0000								
LTD	0.3318	-0.152	1.0000							
OEOIR	-0.1250	-0.057	-0.236	1.0000						
IR	0.0120	0.0706	-0.029	0.0321	1.0000					
LIR	0.2573	-0.0245	-0.064	0.0938	-0.246	1.0000				
GDP	0.0509	-0.0948	0.0922	0.0235	0.0672	-0.644	1.0000			
GovExp	-0.1501	-0.1652	0.2357	-0.240	-0.201	-0.562	0.4067	1.0000		
M2	-0.1826	-0.0187	-0.058	0.0871	-0.392	0.4443	-0.327	-0.1370	1.0000	
Tax rate	0.5329	-0.2983	0.3596	-0.408	-0.033	0.0644	0.1500	0.1967	-0.270	1.0000

Source: Table by authors

The correlation result in the above table shows return on asset, operating expense to operating income, government expenditure and broad money supply, have negative correlation with nonperforming loans of Ethiopian commercial banks. It refers that when these ratio increases, nonperforming loan of the banks will be go down. However, loan to deposit ratio, average lending rate, effective tax rate, growth domestic product, inflation rate, have positive correlation with nonperforming loans which indicates that while these ratio decreases, at the same time nonperforming loan of the bank will be decrease and vice versa. The correlation analysis results presented in the table clearly show no multicollinearity issues among the explanatory variables, as none of the values exceed the 0.8 threshold. Gujarati (2004) observes that if the correlation is 0.8 or higher, there is a serious issue with multicollinearity.

4.3. Choosing Random Effect Vs Fixed Effect Model

The study's suitability for a fixed-or random-effects model was determined using the Hausman test. Both the null and alternative hypotheses propose different models; the former states that fixed effects is superior and the latter states that random effects is more suitable. If the p-value is larger than 0.05, the result is not statistically significant, and the random effects model is appropriate; otherwise, another model is used. On the other hand, the fixed effects model would be supported by a p-value lower than 0.05. This study yielded a p-value of 0.6378, which is significantly higher than the significance level of 0.05. It follows that the random effects model is appropriate for the investigation and that the result is negligible, therefore accepting the null hypothesis.

4.4. Test for Classical Linear Regression Model Assumptions

As noted by Brooks (2008), when the key assumptions hold true, it ensures that the model incorporates all relevant data. However, violations of these assumptions suggest that some information might be excluded from the model. Therefore, prior to assessing the significance of the slopes and interpreting the regression results, it is crucial to conduct tests for stationarity, normality, multicollinearity, autocorrelation, and heteroskedasticity. These tests help detect any potential data issues and ensure the model's fitness and the overall quality of the research.

The test of stationary shows that the variables considered in this study are stationary at levels— ROA, LTD, OEOIR, LIR, GDP, Gov Exp, and M2 are stationary at level and the remaining variable IR are stationary at order one which is not the serious problem. The result of the Levin-Lin-Chu unit-root test for the variables test statistics shows that this study rejects the null hypothesis of the variable's non-stationary or presence of panel unit root. Normality Test: The Jarque-Bera test indicated no evidence of non-normality (p-value = 0.1862), supported by skewness (0.0736) and kurtosis (0.7692) within the acceptable range (-1.0 to +1.0). Residuals were therefore normally distributed. Multicollinearity Test: Variance Inflation Factors (VIF) confirmed no multicollinearity issues among independent variables. The average VIF was 1.82, well below the threshold of 10. Accordingly, in order to detect the heteroskedasticity problems, the Breusch-Pagan test was utilized in this study. This test states that if the p-value is significant at 95% confidence interval, the data has heteroskedasticity problem, in this study the p-value is below 0.05 so there is heteroskedasticity problem. To control and get efficient and consistent results the researcher runs the FGLS model which is the appropriate. To check the presence of autocorrelation in the study, the Wooldridge test used and confirmed no autocorrelation (p-value=0.4724).

4.5. Result of Regression Analysis

This section presents the regression result of random effect and feasible generalized model that made to examine the determinant of NPLs of commercial banks in Ethiopia. As a result, the regression result was obtained, and the coefficients of the variables were estimated using Stata-17 software. As previously indicated in the model selection section, the random effect regression model was chosen. FGLS is an appropriate model for this investigation because it addresses endogeneity difficulties while also producing consistent results.

Table 4. Results of Random effect and GMM regression model

Random effect result				FGLS result		
Variable	Coefficient	Standard error	Prob.*	Coefficient	Standard error	Prob.*
ROA	-1.707914	.5923159	0.004	-1.707914	.5664379	0.003
LTD	.1719223	.0581082	0.003	.1719223	.0555695	0.002
OEOIR	-.0621942	.1516783	0.682	-.0621942	.1450515	0.668
IR	-.0103003	.083285	0.902	-.0103003	.0796463	0.897
LIR	4.813602	1.758477	0.006	4.813602	1.68165	0.004
GDP	1.669413	.7552583	0.027	1.669413	.7222615	0.021
GovExp	-.6845389	.3002872	0.023	-.6845389	.2871678	0.017

M2	-.3446484	.1480942	0.020	-.3446484	.1416241	0.015
Tax rate	.0121718	.003845	0.002	.0121718	.0036773	0.001
Constant	-.5240294	.2900983	0.071	-.5240294	.2774241	0.059
R-Squared = 0.4214			Wald chi2(9) = 111.39			
Prob (F-Statistic) = 0.0000			Prob > chi2 = 0.0000			

Source: Table by authors

The above table demonstrates the results and level of significant for random and feasible generalized least square models. However, in this study the feasible generalized least square estimation technique is preferred as the estimation technique which yields efficient and consistent results. The beta coefficient may be negative or positive; beta indicates that each variable's level of influence on the dependent variable. P-value indicates at what percentage or precession level of each variable is significant. Wald chi2 implies coefficients of explanatory variables are different from zero so, it suggested that a change in nonperforming loans of commercial banks are due to change in the explanatory variables. Accordingly, F-statistics of the model has a p-value of 0.0000; this implies that all selected explanatory variables can affect the level of NPLs in common.

The study analyzed the impact of bank-specific and macroeconomic factors on NPLs using a feasible generalized least square model as shown in Table 4. Among the bank-specific factors, ROA and OEOIR demonstrated negative effects on NPLs, with coefficients of -1.7079 and -0.0622, respectively, indicating that a 1% increase in ROA or OEOIR would reduce NPLs by 1.7079% and 0.0622%. Conversely, LTD had a positive effect, with a coefficient of 0.1719, implying that a 1% increase in LTD would raise NPLs by 0.1719%. For macroeconomic factors, LIR (4.8136) and GDP (1.6694) positively influenced NPLs, while IR (-0.0103), Government Expenditure (-0.6845), and M2 (-0.3446) had negative impacts. The effective tax rate also showed a small positive effect on NPLs, with a coefficient of 0.0122. In terms of significance, ROA, LTD, LIR, GDP, Government Expenditure, M2, and the effective tax rate exhibited statistically significant impacts on NPLs, with p-values below 0.05. However, OEOIR ($p = 0.668$) and IR ($p = 0.897$) were not statistically significant.

4.6. Discussion of Results

Building on prior studies and the findings of this research, this section presents a detailed discussion of the results obtained through the FGLS model, focusing on their implications for the level of Non-Performing Loans (NPLs) in Ethiopian commercial banks. By referring to existing literature, each explanatory variable is analyzed in terms of its influence on NPLs, offering a comparative view against both empirical and theoretical frameworks.

Return on Asset (ROA) and NPLs; The estimated coefficient for the bank's Return on Assets (ROA) indicates a negative relationship with non-performing loans (NPLs). The ROA coefficient was -0.3529162, highlighting its negative effect on NPL levels. This suggests that for every 1% increase in bank profitability, measured by ROA, there is a corresponding 0.3529162% decrease in NPL levels, assuming all other factors remain constant. The results align with previous predictions and theories, which suggest that more profitable banks tend to engage in fewer risky activities, as they are under less pressure to increase income, thereby reducing the level of (NPLs) (Barth et al., 2004; Berger & DeYoung, 1997). In this context, it can be concluded that as the financial performance (profitability) of Ethiopian banks improves, their likelihood of engaging in risky activities diminishes, which, in turn, reduces the probability of loans becoming non-performing. Therefore, the results show that the financial performance of the bank influences the level of non-performing loans in Ethiopian commercial banks. This result agreed with the prior research of (Boudriga et al., 2009; Godlewski, 2011; Louzis et al., 2012).

Loan to deposit (LTD) and NPLs; Table 4 showed that the coefficient and test statistics of loan to deposit is 0.1719223 and 0.002 respectively. This means, LTD is statistically significant at 5% significant level and holding other factors constant, a percentage change in Loan to deposit will result a .1719223 percent change of Ethiopian commercial banks NPL in the same direction. This result is consistent with expected result for the study and also conform the findings of Swamy (2012), Jiménez & Saurina (2005), Sinkey & Greenawalt (1991), Makri et al. (2014), Saba et al. (2012) and Louzis et al. (2012) found that there is a negative relationship between LTD and NPLs. A positive relationship between non- performing loans

and loan to total asset ratio implies that a rapid expansion of loan leads the lower the quality assets the banks possess, the higher the NPL (not able to generate income). A positive significant effect of loan to deposit on Ethiopian commercial banks of NPL suggest that borrower wants loan and gives priority to banks provide loan with high interest rate rather than not provide loan. Ethiopian commercial banks to spread their customer base and to increase their deposit use loan as an enticement to attract a new customer.

Lending interest rate and NPLs; Table 4 showed that the coefficient and test statistics of LIR is 4.813602 and 0.004 respectively. The coefficient estimate of interest rate (measured by the average lending rate of Ethiopian commercial banks) was positive which was in accordance with prior expectation and the findings of (Fofack, 2005; Jiménez & Saurina, 2005; Sinkey & Greenawalt, 1991). This implies that holding other factors constant, a percentage change in LIR will result a 4.813602 percent change of Ethiopian commercial banks NPL in the same direction. That means as interest rates rise, prudent borrowers are more likely to decide that it would be unwise to borrow, whereas borrowers with the riskiest investment projects are often those who are willing to pay the highest interest rates. Hence, higher interest rate leads to greater adverse selection that increases the likelihood that the lender is lending to a bad credit risk which ultimately increases the volume of banks NPLs.

Gross domestic product and NPLs; The regression result of FGLS model in the above table 4 is inconsistent with the hypothesis developed by the researcher. The study hypothesized that there is a negative association between GDP and NPLs of banks. Contrary to the hypothesis, the estimated coefficients and test statistics of ROA was 1.669413 and 0.021 respectively. This result shows positive and statistically significant impact of GDP on the levels of NPLs and implies that for a percentage change in GDP, keeping the other thing constant had resulted 1.669413 unit changes on the level of NPLs in the same direction. The finding of the study is consistent with (Swamy, 2012). The argument for the positive relationship between the variables is that the improvement in our real economy, within the period under consideration was not substantial enough to lead to a reduction in the NPLs. This may be due to the fact that credit facilities obtained from the banks were not properly utilized in productive activities or it may be due to customers operating in a harsh economic environment.

Government Expenditure (Gov Exp) and NPLs; The hypothetical effect that the study developed is not consistent with the regression result of the GMM model in Table 4 above. The study postulated a positive correlation between Gov Exp and bank non-performing loans (NPLs). The coefficient of Gov Exp, in contrast to the hypothesis, was -0.3574469. Based on this data, it can be concluded that Gov Exp has a statistically significant negative impact on NPL levels. This suggests that a 0.3574469 percent change in the level of NPLs was the result of a percentage change in Gov Exp held constant with respect to the other variable. The result of this study confirms the arguments of (Touny & Shehab, 2015). This suggests that government spending has a negative impact on the amount of non-performing loans (NPLs). Table 4 illustrates the correlation between a low level of NPLs ratio and an increase in government spending. According to this relationship, an increase in government spending corresponds to a rise in employee pay and benefits, which helps to lower the employees' debt load.

Broad Money Supply (M2) and NPLs; The coefficient for M2 is -0.1015197, as Table 4 demonstrates. This indicates that, while all other variables remain unchanged, a change in M2 will have the opposite effect on Ethiopian commercial banks' non-performing loans (NPLs), changing by 0.1015197 percent. According to this finding, an expansionary monetary policy will lower interest rates, which in turn reduces the cost of borrowing. Additionally, a rise in the money supply will encourage spending and investment, which will raise income and improve debtors' capacity to repay their loans. This finding conforms with the results of (Ahmad & Ariff, 2008; Nikolaidou & Vogiazas, 2014).

Effective Tax Rate (ETR) and NPLs; This study hypothetical effect is supported by the regression result of the GMM model in Table 4 above. The study proposed a positive correlation between bank NPLs and ETR. The coefficient of ETR in contrast to the hypothesis, was 0.3283027. This finding demonstrates that ETR has a positive and statistically significant effect on NPL levels. It suggests that, for every percentage change in ETR, the level of NPLs changed by 0.3283027 percent in the same direction while the other variable remained constant. The result of this study confirms the arguments of (Albertazzi & Gambacorta, 2006; Khan et al., 2018). This suggests that at some point, Ethiopia's high income tax rates contributed to the country's higher non-performing loan (NPL) levels in commercial banks. This suggests that when a bank transfers its tax burden to borrowers by raising fees and other commissions and loan

prices, the borrowers pay the banks' tax burden as compensation and also owe the government tax. This is supported by the positive and statistically significant influence of the effective tax rate on commercial bank non-performing loans (NPLs). As a result, debtors who bear this double burden are unable to make their payments.

5. Conclusions and Suggestions

5.1. Conclusion

The main objective of this study was to examine the determinants of nonperforming loans (NPLs) of commercial banks in Ethiopia based on panel data analysis on the time period from 2008 to 2022. The data were analyzed by using FGLS Model. The study found out that return on asset, loan to deposit ratio, lending rate, gross domestic product, government expenditure, broad money supply and effective tax rate had statistically significant effect on the level of NPLs. However, the results of FGLS regression model revealed operating expense to operating income ratio and inflation rate had statistically insignificant effect on the level of NPLs of commercial banks in Ethiopia for the period under consideration.

The results further demonstrated that bank profitability, measured by return on assets (ROA), has a significant negative impact on NPL levels. This implies that as Ethiopian commercial banks effectively manage their assets, they are less likely to engage in high-risk activities, which helps mitigate the occurrence of non-performing loans. Profitable banks are generally in a stronger financial position and, as a result, have less pressure to pursue risky ventures to generate income. Consequently, higher profitability contributes to a more stable loan portfolio, reducing credit risk and minimizing NPLs. However, the LTD has positive and statistically significant impact on NPLs. This indicates Ethiopian commercial banks to spread their customer base and to increase their deposit, use loan as an enticement to attract a new customer and thus resulted the occurrence NPLs for commercial banks in the country.

The finding of lending interest rate and gross domestic product are a factor that has positive impact on the levels of NPLs of commercial banks in Ethiopia as per the regression result in this study. This implies higher interest rate leads to greater adverse selection that increases the likelihood that the lender is lending to a bad credit risk which ultimately increases the volume of banks NPLs and the result of gross domestic product indicates that that the improvement in our real economy, within the period under consideration was not substantial enough to lead to a reduction in the NPLs. Moreover, the study's regression results indicate that government expenditure has a negative effect on the NPL levels of Ethiopian commercial banks. Increased government spending often reflects higher employee compensation and greater social benefit disbursements, which help reduce the debt burden on employees and, consequently, lower NPLs. Similarly, the broad money supply also exerts a negative influence on NPL levels, suggesting that an expansionary monetary policy stimulates investment, thereby decreasing the proportion of non-performing loans. Lastly, the effective tax rate was found to have a positive impact on NPL levels. Higher taxes place additional financial strain on borrowers, increasing the likelihood of defaults among commercial banks in Ethiopia.

5.2. Suggestions

Based on the findings and conclusions of the regression analysis, the following Suggestions are proposed. First and for most, bank management and loan officers should always give a serious attention to the health of asset quality of banks specifically loan performance for prevention of loans loss. In order to reduce the chance of occurrence of NPLs; it is better for the bank managers to give due emphasis on the asset management decision. Thus if assets well managed, financial performance of Ethiopian banks increase will reduce from engaging in risky activities resulted in reduction in the level of NPLs.

With regard to loan to deposit ratio; The researcher recommended that Ethiopian commercial banks would eliminate loan expansion related problems such as poor screening and lending and make the loan procedures easy which means provide loans for high depositors and have more transactions with familiar rather than fulfilled written loan procedure criteria in order to hold customers. Due to the above-mentioned reasons, increase loan disbursement practice of Ethiopian commercial banks leads to an increase the volume of NPLs. Therefore, this study recommends that Ethiopian Commercial Banks

balance their loan in proportion to customers' deposits. Lending rate has an influential impact on the level of NPLs. Thus, the maximum and minimum lending rate is fixed by the NBE, bank management has to impose moderate lending rate in between and compensate its costs through increasing fees and other commission charges and bank management would encourage to diversify more by adopting more non-interest income activities.

An increase of government spending is associated with a low level of NPLs. The government increase spending on social benefits which in turn contributes to alleviate the debt burden of these employees. So as to reduce NPLs the government would adopt expansionary fiscal policy. As banking sectors shift their tax burden to their borrowers, borrowers' ability to repay their debt would be reduced and then results in the occurrence of NPLs. Thus, in order to reduce the level of NPLs, it is better for the bank management either to avoid or substitute shifting of its tax burden by rearranging its financial affairs like reinvesting dividend payment (making cash payments to shareholders by repurchasing their own shares) and increasing deduction like interest expense. And the government would reduce tax so as to curtail NPLs.

Finally, this study recommends national bank of Ethiopia to adopt expansionary monetary policy in order to stimulate investment and consumption and consequently will increase the income and therefore increase the ability of debtors to meet their loan obligations.

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